

FROM HERE, HEALTH

Case Studies in Diving Medicine

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Module C05: Diving Medicine

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Paper 1; Diving medicine, principles and evidence

The fitness to work assessment framework of HSE UK¹, takes into account the unique working environment of commercial diving, the physical and mental requirements of work, and the acute and long term effects that such activity may have on the diver. The diver is exposed to the effects of both pressure and immersion, which can aggravate a pre-existing condition, and lead to the development of new ones.

A. General medical considerations

An initial questionnaire and fact sheet will help to identify any issues, which preclude the candidate from undertaking commercial diving activity.

B. Mental health

A diver should be free from any psychiatric illness and have normal cognitive and psychomotor abilities². Some conditions may impact the safety of other personnel and need further specialist assessment.

C. Respiratory System

Asthma if not properly controlled can lead to pulmonary barotrauma³. Pre-existing conditions can lead to serious damage to the body later on⁴, and hence should be appropriately addressed.

D. CVS

Certain conditions can lead to the increase incidence of diving accidents, and needs proper redressal. High blood pressure increases the chances of decompression sickness⁵, IHD can lead to fatalities⁶, congenital conditions can lead to a myriad of problems, and has to be assessed on case by case basis⁷. Underwater dysrhythmias can lead to disorientation, choking, pulmonary oedema and barotrauma⁸. A PFO can predispose to various DCI, including neurologic, cardiac and other conditions⁹

E. Nervous System

Epilepsy if uncontrolled can lead to fatality¹⁰, any neurological conditions that has chance to recur underwater, has to be carefully excluded. Migraine and motion sickness may be indicative of other serious conditions¹¹. Significant head injury carries increased risk of accidents¹².

F. Musculoskeletal System

Suspected cases of Dysbaric Osteonecrosis need assessment¹³, as the condition is associated with significant morbidity and collapse of skeletal structures.

G. ENT

Some of the most common medical conditions that occur with deep sea diving and that can lead to safety issues, including barotrauma, vertigo, etc., are attributable to ENT conditions¹⁴. As such these organs must be as free of pathology as possible.

H. Eye

Any decrease in visual acuity can lead to underwater problems, as the diver often has to assess parameters based on visual cues¹⁵, and hence should be within acceptable range.

I. Dental

To prevent complications, the dental health of the diver needs to be assessed and suitably addressed¹⁶. This will help to reduce incidences of barodontalgia, odontocrexia, and other related conditions¹⁷.

J. Endocrine System

Uncontrolled diabetes, or evidence of complications, are hazards for saturation diving, and hence will lead to disqualification. There is a long history of accidents, related to these conditions¹⁸. Controlled thyroid disease is currently an acceptable risk factor, provided cardiac complications have not developed. Systemic steroid therapy is associated with significant underwater risks, and has to be disqualified.

K. Genitourinary, Gastrointestinal, and other considerations.

Abnormal urine, blood, renal function tests should be carefully assessed for any remediation steps. Significant pathology will lead to disqualification. Active IBD, pancreatitis, gall bladder pathologies, and surgical conditions will require assessment by specialists for approval or disqualification. Any skin condition that may affect thermoregulation, increases risk of compromise of diving operations and are reason for disqualification. Sickle cell and thalassaemia patients remain unfit for diving.

Paper 2: Assessment of the diving environment

Thermal conditions

A deep-sea dive can lead to cold water immersion and its effects, which can significantly affect the safety of the diver. Cold shock can lead to panic and drowning, and to dysrhythmias.

Immersion diuresis, Circum-rescue collapse are other known associated conditions. Immersion diuresis can lead to loss of insulation and dehydration¹⁹⁻²¹. Mental and physical performance tend to deteriorate^{19,22}.

Safety measure that can be put in place, are provision of appropriate PPE, additional insulation of the same, provisions for diver warming, Breathing Gas warming arrangements. Additionally, divers must undergo cold weather training, including dry suit training, and be aware of the issues and procedures during distress^{20,23}.

In hot environments, diver overheating and hyperthermia can occur. Appropriate cooling techniques should be used and supervisors must be aware of the risks involved.

Marine Creatures

Supervisors and Medical Officers must be aware of the biological hazards in the vicinity of the diving activity. Sharks, and other predators, can cause bite injuries. Appropriate PPE can protect to some degree, awareness of dangers involved, avoidance and deterrence also play a part²⁴.

Some other marine creatures can cause envenomation, poisoning and intoxication. These are specific to particular geographical areas. The mode of injury can be stings, shocks, envenomation, etc. A proper knowledge of the various dangerous lifeforms, can help to avoid being affected^{25,26}.

Saturation diving

The decompression chamber, either deck or submersible, forms an important part of offshore diving operations. Divers need to stay for long periods to get to saturation levels, and are confined within a chamber, which is pressurised to simulate diving conditions. During this subaquatic stay, the divers need to breathe complex breathing gases, and observe meticulous regimens regarding, diet, hygiene, etc. The requirements of maintaining the breathing environment, within narrow ranges of gaseous mixtures, temperature, humidity, etc., are meticulous. Any change in these parameters can significantly change the partial pressure of fractional components leading to catastrophic consequences. Hence elaborate filtering, monitoring, feedback and supply systems needs to be in place. Backup of all requirements is also essential^{27,28}.

Paper 3: Medical planning for diving activity at remote locations; No DDC available.

Assessment:

1. Location risk assessment:

A. Location: How far from nearest medical facilities and the requirement of travelling to these facilities. This should be given due consideration as the chances of developing arterial gas embolism, decompression sickness will require recompression in a hyperbaric chamber.

B. Environmental consideration:

Condition of tidal waves, surface conditions, air and water temperature, potential effects of weather exposure. As per Paper 2, thermal conditions can lead to hypothermia, immersion diuresis, cold shock, dysrhythmia, and deterioration of mental and physical performance.

C. Underwater hazards:

Harmful biological life, visibility, pollution, chances of injury from natural and manmade disasters, entrapment and dangers from the underwater activity itself. Any predators that can bite, and other biological forms that can envenomate, intoxicate, or cause physical injury needs to be taken into account.

The work site itself, may expose the diver to entrapment, falling debris, physical objects.

Depending on the hazards, the medical plan should include provisions for emergency treatment of hypothermia, marine life attacks and injuries.

2. Task and Operational risk assessment

The underwater activity may require divers to stay deeper and longer to fulfil tasks. This may increase the chances of breathing gas, immersion and hyperbaric related injuries including barotrauma, inert gas narcosis, CO poisoning, oxygen toxicity, AGE, DCS, etc. Repetitive dives may be required, increase nitrogen residual times.

A. Diving technique:

1. Surface supplied or Scuba.
2. Saturation diving.
3. Breathing gas.

B. Emergency Response Plan

Detailed plans on how a casualty will be evacuated, logistical considerations, MEDEVAC co-ordination charts, communication protocols should be available.

C. Medical Support^{29,30}

The level of medical support should take into consideration of likely incidences. Full list of medical items should be available and the need for a decompression chamber should be given due consideration. Adequately trained medical support personnel should be available.

The list of items to be held at the dive site should be according to DMAC recommendation and should cover the following aspects, and the complexity of the diving task.

1. General diagnostic equipment, dressing and sterile supplies, thoracocentesis and urinary catheterization sets.
2. Intravenous and resuscitation equipment.
3. Drugs for anaesthesia, analgesia, nausea and vomiting, allergy, psychiatric conditions, resuscitation, burn care and antibiotics.

No Deck Diving Chamber or none within 12-24 hours. Treatment requiring recompression varies as per the emergency involved:

1. Excess bottom time: Use Air decompression table.
2. Loss of oxygen supply in water: Continue decompression on air in water.
3. CNS Oxygen toxicity: Continue air decompression in water at 20 fsw.
4. Oxygen convulsion: Shift to air, and continue life support procedures.
5. DCS: In water recompression using oxygen, following alternative protocol. If using air, can use recommended treatment tables and figures from US Navy diving manual.

Paper 4: Recompression Chamber within 60 minutes of evacuation time (reasonable time frame).

A decision to transport the casualty to the nearest hyperbaric facility is made. The casualty is put on 100% oxygen, and made to lie in supine position. Avoid putting in head down position. The casualty should be kept warm and continuously monitored for obstructed airway, apnea, cardiac arrest or shock³¹.

During transport, the casualty should be on 100% oxygen, iv fluids should be started, and the MEDEVAC plan should be initiated. The aircraft should fly at less than 1000 ft, and the pressure should be at least 1 ATM. Emergency Evacuation Hyperbaric Stretcher can be useful.

The hyperbaric facility should be informed regarding the condition of the casualty and requested to keep all resources in standby

Paper 5: Deck Diving Chamber (DDC) available.

All cases of medical emergencies that will benefit from hyperbaric therapy should be transferred to the DDC, and treatment tables (TT) as found in the US NAVY Diving Manual, Volume 5(USNDM), should be used. The tender should be able to keep surface interval to less than 5 minutes.

Arterial Gas Embolism:

Use Fig. 17-1 and TT6 of USNDM. If unconscious follow ACLS protocols and use CPR and AED. If pulse returns transfer the casualty to the DDC, and keep pressure to 30 fsw.

DCS Type 1:

Use Fig 17-2 and TT6

DCS Type 2:

Use Fig 17-1 and TT6, if the symptoms become severe shift to TT6A

Symptomatic omitted decompression:

Compress to 60 fsw and use TT6, 6A or 8, according to depth from which ascent occurred.

General guidelines:

Treating with oxygen always preferable.

Use Air treatment tables when oxygen delivery failure has occurred or oxygen toxicity is found.

Use oxygen TT5, 6, 6A, 4 or 7. Use Air TT1A, 2A or 3.

Special applicability notes on Treatment Tables and figures:

TT5 with Fig 17-4: Type 1 DCS/asymptomatic omitted decompression/Gas gangrene/CO poisoning.

TT6 with Fig 17-5: AGE/Type 2 DCS/unrelieved Type 1 DCS/Cutis Marmorata/CO poisoning/symptomatic uncontrolled ascent.

TT6A with Fig 17-6: Severe or unchanged AGE or DCS.

TT4 with Fig 17-7: Shifted from TT6A, if it is believed, casualty will receive additional benefit at depth of significant relief not to exceed 165 fsw.

TT7 with Fig 17-8: extension of other tables, in a last measure attempt to improve the condition of a casualty who is not responding to other tables, nearing completion of schedule.

TT8 with Fig 17-9: Treatment of symptomatic patients who had a deep uncontrolled ascent, and has missed more than 60 minutes of decompression.

TT9 with Fig 17-10: Residual symptoms, CO or cyanide poisoning, smoke inhalation.

Environmental control and other considerations:

Paper 6: Short Cases

Case 1

The most likely cause is hypoxia. An oxygen saturation probe can confirm the diagnosis, if below 94%. He should be given basic first aid and 100% oxygen, using an oxygen delivery system. Further management is focused on preventing the condition from happening again:

1. Supply gas should be checked for oxygen content.
2. UBA oxygen sensor malfunction; diver should be reminded to check the sensors for possible malfunction.
3. Purge MK-25 UBA breathing bags.
4. Check MK-16 oxygen addition valve.
5. Clear all blockages of the breathing system, and air passages.

Case 2

A case of hypercapnia. End tidal CO₂ measurement can help to confirm. The casualty should be advised to reduce exertion, and ventilation to his helmet and lungs should be increased. If the cause is a defect in his breathing equipment, he should be shifted to an alternate breathing source. Further management is focused on prevention:

1. CO₂ absorbing cannister should be carefully filled, dive duration should be within prescribed limit of cannister use.
2. Compressor inlet should be checked for correct placement.
3. Breathing hoses should be properly installed.

4. Other causes could be increased dead space, increased breathing resistance and increased oxygen partial pressure.

Case 3

A case of both Type 1 and 2 DCS. As he has joint pain, he is suffering from Type 1 DCS. But as there are skin symptoms with altered neurological sensation, he also has type 2 DCS. Rx according to Fig 17-1 and TT6. The patient should be shifted to the DDC and compressed to 60fsw and given 100% oxygen. If condition improves start TT6. If no improvement shifts to TT6A after compressing to dept of relief on air. Further management can be according to TT6A, or may have to be shifted to TT4 or TT7 depending on response.

Case 4

This casualty is depicting both CNS and Pulmonary oxygen toxicity. The CNS symptoms are visual disturbance, sensation of abnormality, respiratory difficulty, loss of consciousness.

The Pulmonary symptoms are retrosternal chest pain.

The prevention of these cases is to carefully mix the gases, so that the ppO₂ does not exceed 1.4 ATA. The maximum depth and the planned bottom time should not be exceeded, to prevent further CNS oxygen toxicity symptoms. Since the casualty has developed Pulmonary symptoms, he should avoid NITROX diving until resolution of symptoms.

Case 5

A case of inner ear barotrauma. The casualty had tried vigorous ear manoeuvres. This could have caused thoracic overpressure being transmitted to CSF and leakage of perilymph into

the middle ear. Middle ear barotrauma can also be present. There is also deafness, that could be sensorineural hearing loss. Haemorrhage and labyrinthine tear are other hypotheses^{14,32}.

Although electronystagmography and pure tone audiometry form part of the investigations, confirmation required surgical exploration. Conservative management can be tried, and there is consensus, to let these divers, return to diving while proscribing a cautious approach to the same³³.

Case 6-Unsolved.

Case 7

This casualty suffered from hypoxia of ascent³⁴, because the ppO₂ dropped as he moved upwards. The two main reasons are hyperventilation before diving and miscalculation of bottom time. He should be properly tutored regarding safe limits, maintain carbohydrate reserves, and avoid unsafe practices.

He later developed saltwater aspiration syndrome, as characterised by SOB and pyrexia. He is better referred to a respiratory unit to monitor for resolution or treatment for cough, bronchospasm, ARDS, pneumonia, electrolyte disturbances if they develop³⁵.

Case 8

A case of nitrogen narcosis, due to the effects of breathing nitrogen-oxygen mixtures with ppN₂ exceeding 4 ATA. He should be brought up to a shallower depth, or brought to the surface.

Management for new trainees are to keep them at shallower depth, provide information about nitrogen narcosis, and remind them to be vigilant regarding any abnormal feeling, thought or sensation they may have and to ascent by 10 fsw at a time to avoid the narcosis. Experienced

divers can manage at larger depths without ill effects, but they too need to remain alert regarding any possible effects as described above.

Case 9

A case of arterial gas embolism, with possible cerebral involvement. After checking the ABCs, he must be treated in a recompression chamber using Fig 17-1 and recompressed to 60 fsw.

Depending on response he may be continued on TT6, 6A, 4 or 7. Later on further investigations can include transoesophageal echocardiography for embolus detection, CT scan of chest, ETCO₂.

Consider existence of PFO. A complete haematological profile is also required.

Management items are:

1. ABC management.
2. Central line aspiration of right heart.
3. 100 % O₂ NRB.
4. Inotropic support.
5. Durant's manoeuvre- left lateral decubitus with Trendelenburg position.
6. Hyperbaric therapy.

Case 10- Unsolved.

Case 11

The diver probably experienced suit squeeze. This happens, when enough air is not added to the suit, during descent to adjust for the compression of air inside the suit. This will result in the folds pressing on the skin, reduction in insulation, difficulty in movement. Bruising of the skin

can occur. The problem can be mitigated, by remembering to inflate the suit, from a low pressure gas supply. The drysuit should be periodically checked for any damage to the fabric, seals, valves, zippers, etc.

Case 12

A case of pulmonary immersion oedema. Several conditions may have contributed to this including cold water, exertion, mild hypertension, and overhydration. Pulse oximeter reading may show low saturation, and PaO₂ may be decreased. ECG may show tachycardia.

Treatment is with 100% Oxygen, and diuretics.

Case 13

The casualty manifests CNS oxygen toxicity. This happens when the diver is exposed to ppO₂ of 2.3(dry) or 1.3(wet). A number of factors, may have influenced this including individual susceptibility, CO₂ retention, exercise, immersion in water, depth and duration of dive, and exceeding oxygen exposure times. The diver in all probability, made a mistake, and changed to 80% mixture, when changing cylinder underwater.

Since the diver has already lost his demand valve, and is unconscious, he is best sent to the surface and ABC initiated. A later investigation for suspected AGE should also be initiate.

Toxicity can be prevented by:

1. Remaining vigilant of correct BG cylinders.
2. Observe depth-time limits.
3. Avoid excessive exertion.

4. Remain vigilant of any abnormal symptoms.
5. Using periodic air breaks.

Case 14

A case of retinal detachment or optic nerve compression, because of expansion of gases, leading to sinus barotrauma. Since he regained vision, it is probably a case of ON compression getting resolved, due to the sinus contents getting extruded. Barotrauma of descent led to trapping of gases, which expanded on ascent.

Treatment is topical steroids, painkillers, decongestants, and ENT referral. Hyperbaric work environments must be avoided, until the pathology pinpointed, obstruction resolved, and suitable remedy initiated. Recurrent cases may require surgery.

Case 15

The diver is suffering from delayed onset Type 2 DCS, with spinal cord involvement. He is already at 160 fsw, in a pressurised chamber. This case will benefit by using Fig 13-13. The DCS occurred without excursion and hence the casualty should be recompressed at 5 FPM to depth of distinct improvement. If improvement occurs within 10 mins, start Rx treatment gas with oxygen at required ATA, and as per prescribed schedule. The treatment gas should be administered for at least 2 hours. If no improvement occurs, deeper recompression may be authorized by the DMO, and then same flowchart followed. The diver should remain at relief depth for at least 12 hours and no upward excursion is permitted. Decompression then can be resumed as per Table 13-9.

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